

ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities

Work Package WP7

Report on the first ATRIUM Mutual Learning Exercise (GoTriple)

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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
ATRIUM	Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities
BASE	Bielefeld Academic Search Engine
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
DNB	Deutsche Nationalbibliothek (German National Library)
DoA	Description of Action
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
EDM	Europeana Data Model
EKT	Ethniko Kentro Tekmiriōsis (National Documentation Centre of Greece)
EU	European Union
FASCA	Facilitating Scholarly Communication Analysis through GoTriple Pipeline
FECYT	Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología (Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology)
GRAPHIA	Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities
H2020	Horizon 2020 (European Union's Research and Innovation Programme)
IBL PAN	Instytut Badań Literackich Polskiej Akademii Nauk (The Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences)
INFRAEOSC	European Open Science Cloud Infrastructure (funding call in H2020)
LLM	Large Language Model
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
MARC-21	Machine-Readable Cataloging (version21)

MLE	Mutual Learning Exercise
MUNCYT	Museo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología de España (National Museum of Science and Technology)
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
RECYT	Repositorio Español de Ciencia y Tecnología (Spanish Science and Technology Repository)
PIDs	Persistent Identifiers
PSNC	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center
RI	Research infrastructure
SCRE	Semantic Content Retrieval Engine
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TRIPLE	Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration
UCM	Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Complutense University of Madrid)
UNE	Unión de Editoriales Universitarias Españolas (Spanish University Publishers Association)
XML	Extensible Markup Language
ZRC SAZU	Znanstvenoraziskovalni center Slovenske akademije znanosti in umetnosti (Scientific Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts)

Executive Summary

This report summarises the outcomes of the first **Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE)** organised as part of the **ATRIUM** project. The event was held on **April 29, 2025, in Madrid, Spain**, and focused on the **GoTriple service**, a multilingual discovery platform for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) offered by OPERAS Research Infrastructure. The purpose of the MLE was to **promote mutual learning and the exchange of experiences** between service and data providers.

The event logistics were affected by a **historic blackout** the day before, which prevented participants from four invited institutions from attending. Although some adjustments to the exercises were necessary, the first ATRIUM MLE was carried out successfully.

Main Objective

The primary goal of the workshop was to gather **feedback from data providers** to **support the enhancement of the GoTriple service** and contribute to the development of **best practices for managing digital services in the SSH domain**. The MLE involved representatives from both **current and potential data providers** from institutions in Spain, Poland, and the Netherlands, as well as representatives from the GoTriple team. The format included discussions and interactive sessions, structured around **three main exercises** focusing on data quality, the data journey in GoTriple, and the future of the platform and its community. Exercise 1 focused on the **self-assessment** of institutional metadata quality and management practices. Exercise 2 examined the **technical process of data ingestion, enrichment, and presentation** within the GoTriple platform. Exercise 3 concerned the **future directions** for GoTriple and strategies for strengthening the **data provider community**.

Key Takeaways

The Mutual Learning Exercise provided valuable insights into the strengths and areas for improvement of the GoTriple platform from the data providers' perspective. Participants noted the **heterogeneity of metadata** provided by different institutions and agreed that GoTriple should take **responsibility for**

preliminary metadata validation and normalisation. There was a general consensus favouring the **Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license for metadata.** Challenges were identified regarding **discipline classification** due to diverse local schemes and the issue of **multilingual metadata**, particularly the lack of translated titles and keywords.

Participants found GoTriple's data ingestion generally problem-free. However, certain metadata elements, such as bibliographic references and funding information, are not consistently indexed or displayed in the user interface, limiting filtering efficiency. The ability to **download search results** and receive detailed **enrichment metrics** was advocated. Core functionalities, such as deduplication and automated classification, were acknowledged as effective. The need to enhance the **analytics dashboard** with specific metrics was also highlighted.

Reflections on the MLE Format

Post-event evaluation of the MLE format indicated that while working with a smaller number of institutions (4 instead of the planned 8) allowed for more intensive and qualitative work, it also led to noticeable participant fatigue. It was suggested that an optimal number of participating institutions for future events is **6-8**. It was highlighted that organising events in languages other than English might be more beneficial when the primary goal is to engage and focus on the local community.

1. What is the Mutual Learning Exercise?

A Mutual Learning Exercise (MLE) is a workshop format designed to promote **mutual learning and the exchange of experiences** among participants. Within the scope of the ATRIUM project¹, the MLE brings together **service and data providers** involved in digital services for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), including aggregators, repositories, and other platforms that manage data contributions from multiple stakeholders. The event also aims to support **service enhancement** and contribute to the **development of best practices for managing digital services** in the SSH domain.

Key characteristics of MLE:

- Each MLE is organised around a specific service, allowing for focused discussions and targeted outcomes.
- It is designed for services that work with external data providers.
- The MLE brings together service and data providers.
- It is recommended to include both current and prospect data providers.

The MLE format includes discussions and interactive sessions in which participants (data providers) critically reflect on key topics such as harvesting and aggregation methods, metadata, data validation, normalization, licensing, or any other issues identified by service providers as priorities for engagement. The mutual learning aspect involves a **two-way exchange of knowledge**, where service providers learn from data providers, and vice versa.

Section 2 shares our experience with organising the first ATRIUM MLE, which took place in Madrid, Spain, on April 29, 2025, and involved participants from institutions in Spain, Poland, and the Netherlands. It was organised around a service offered by OPERAS Research Infrastructure: GoTriple.

¹ <https://atrium-research.eu/>

2. Selected ATRIUM service: GoTriple

2.1 What is GoTriple?

GoTriple² is a multilingual discovery platform for Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). It was the main outcome of the TRIPLE (Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration)³ research project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action (INFRAEOSC-02-2019 Prototyping new Innovative Services). The project ran from October 2019 to March 2023.

GoTriple provides a central access point that allows users to explore, find, access and reuse SSH materials, such as articles, datasets, project descriptions and authors' profiles at a European scale. It is one of the discovery services included in the OPERAS Services Catalogue. OPERAS⁴ is the Research Infrastructure that supports open scholarly communication in SSH in the European Research Area.

GoTriple is in a crucial stage of its development, being sustained by a joint effort of institutions forming the GoTriple Committee and by the resources provided in four EU-funded projects (ATRIUM⁵, FASCA⁶, LUMEN⁷, GRAPHIA⁸), which are currently ongoing. Therefore, the service was selected to be included in the first ATRIUM MLE in order to gather valuable input on how the platform will evolve in the upcoming months.

2.2 Current features

At its heart, GoTriple has a **search engine** whose indexes are fed by a configurable harvesting and processing pipeline that continuously imports and processes metadata for publications and projects from multiple sources (over

² <https://gotriple.eu>

³ <https://project.gotriple.eu/>

⁴ <https://operas-eu.org/>

⁵ <https://atrium-research.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.gotriple.eu/data-services/fascalinitiative>

⁷ <https://lumenproject.eu/>

⁸ <https://graphia-ssh.eu/>

1,400), including large aggregators (BASE, DOAJ, OpenAIRE, Isidore) and national repositories (Hrčak, Biblioteka Nauki, ZRC Sazu, EKT, Recyt or Pombaline).

Currently, the total number of documents indexed in GoTriple is over 19 million. In particular, the support of MARC21 XML data sources, which has been implemented in GoTriple through the ATRIUM project, has allowed the ingestion of over 1.7 million documents metadata from the German National Library (DNB).

Innovative services are integrated into the platform to improve the user experience with personalised **recommendations**, interactive **visualisations**, and the possibility to use a **web annotation tool** to take notes on material found in GoTriple. Finally, users can register on the platform to create a **personal profile**, claim ownership of the indexed documents, find and connect with other SSH researchers.

2.3 How metadata is imported in GoTriple

All the platform's metadata are automatically harvested from various sources, thanks to the metadata ingestion and curation pipeline, named SCRE. This software module helps retrieve, process, and store the metadata of documents (e.g. publications, datasets), projects and authors in the GoTriple indexes.

Basically, SCRE processes metadata by using a pipeline approach: it consists of several specialised services, each dedicated to implement a particular feature. Through them, metadata from the original sources are retrieved, normalised, enriched and finally stored in the GoTriple indexes. In general terms, we can distinguish between:

- Connectors: the components which retrieve metadata about documents, projects and authors from specific data sources;
- Processors, which curate (e.g., normalise and enrich) the original metadata, according to the workflow logic described below;
- Persisters, which finally save the enriched metadata in the platform indexes.

In fact, we can imagine the metadata curation applied in SCRE as a "data flow", starting from the retrieval of the original metadata by a connector, its

normalisation and enrichment while passing through every single processor, and finally the storage of the result in the platform indexes via a persister.

The data flow for documents is presented in the diagram that follows.

Figure 1 - GoTriple data flow for documents

It is important to highlight that data retrieval and processing in GoTriple only involves metadata: the full text of an article, for example, is not actually retrieved but only the URL pointing to it is used and published in GoTriple.

The acquisition of document metadata from various sources can happen in two ways:

- Automatic import via the OAI-PMH standard protocol. Currently, GoTriple supports multiple data models, including Dublin Core, Europeana Data Model (EDM), XOAI and Dublin Core with BASE extension
- Processing of file dumps in MARC-21 XML and OpenAIRE formats.

The first scenario allows a straightforward and quick integration of new data providers in GoTriple, and it is the recommended approach, when feasible. The metadata ingestion process is described in detail in the TRIPLE project deliverable, Report on Data Enrichment.⁹

Data providers from the SSH domain interested in contributing their metadata to GoTriple are recommended to consult the policies and the technical requirements outlined in the GoTriple Content Providers Handbook¹⁰ or contact the Operas Team directly through the Contact page.¹¹

⁹ [TRIPLE Deliverable: D2.5 - Report on Data Enrichment](#)

¹⁰ [Gotriple-handbook-v2_0.docx](#)

¹¹ [Gotriple - Contact](#)

3. MLE design & event description

A task force was established in January 2025 to design and organise the first ATRIUM MLE. The group met weekly and included the following ATRIUM partners as the event's organising team: OPERAS, IBL PAN, PSNC, NET7, and FOXCUB. The first key decisions focused on selecting the venue and co-organiser, defining the participants' profile, and outlining the overall format of the event.

Venue and co-organiser

It was decided to hold the MLE in Spain based on the following criteria:

- Multilingualism is central to GoTriple. Its interface is available in several languages, including Spanish.
- OPERAS has a national node in Spain (OPERAS-ES), led by the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), which agreed to host the event.
- Two of the GoTriple data providers are based in Spain.

Moreover, the collaboration with FECYT aimed to attract more Spanish data providers to GoTriple and increase the number of publications on the platform.

Participants

Recognising the value of mutual learning and experience sharing, the invited participants formed a diverse group, including both current and potential new GoTriple data providers from Spain and abroad.

More specifically, two data providers from outside Spain were invited. Biblioteka Nauki¹², representing Poland's national publications landscape, has already been onboarded as a GoTriple data provider. OAPEN¹³ gathers important data related to Open Access books at the European level. At the time of the MLE's organization, OAPEN was in the early stages of becoming a GoTriple provider, making the event a timely opportunity to accelerate this process.

FECYT took charge of the initial outreach to both existing and prospective providers in Spain. Representatives of current providers readily accepted the

¹² <https://bibliotekanauki.pl/>

¹³ <https://www.oapen.org/home>

invitation: Cordoba University and the Spanish Science and Technology Repository (RECYT). As possible new providers, representatives from the publishing services of four institutions were invited and confirmed their presence to the MLE: Complutense University of Madrid, Polytechnic University of Valencia, Autonomous University of Barcelona and Spanish University Publishers Association (UNE).

However, part of the invited participants were unable to attend due to the historic blackout¹⁴ taking place a few hours before the MLE. The consequences of this power outage for the event organisation and the necessary adaptations are mentioned further below. Thus, the data providers were represented in the MLE by:

- **Biblioteka Nauki** (current provider) - Poland
- **OAPEN** (new provider) - Netherlands
- **RECYT** (current provider) - Spain
- **Complutense University of Madrid** (new provider) - Spain

Representing the service provider:

- **OPERAS**;
- **NET7**, one of GoTriple's main developers and maintainers, based in Italy.
- **FOXSUB**, a French company specialising in data and AI that is also involved in GoTriple.

Format

The MLE exercises were designed collaboratively by the ATRIUM organisers. The goal was to balance individual reflection, small group interactions where data providers could share their experiences, and broader discussions involving the service providers in the light of providing a mutual learning exchange among all participants. The design process followed an iterative approach, using collaborative tools such as Figma and FigJam to prototype, refine, and visualise the sequence of steps. This facilitated real-time alignment among team members and helped ensure a clear, engaging structure for participants on the day of the event.

¹⁴

<https://www.euronews.com/my-europe/2025/04/28/spain-portugal-and-parts-of-france-hit-by-massive-power-outage>

Figure 2: Visual planning board for Exercises 1&2 created in FigJam, showing the iterative structure, timing, and expected outcomes for each step

Following introductory speeches that contextualised the event and GoTriple, an icebreaker activity was prepared to help participants introduce themselves and create a more informal atmosphere. Then, three main exercises were designed to encourage deeper reflection on (meta)data quality, enrichment, aggregation, and interoperability.

The first exercise, titled *“Do I know the data I provide?”*, focused on participants’ (meta)data quality. It was intended to provide an opportunity for self-reflection before discussing their participation in GoTriple. This exercise aimed to help providers assess the quality, consistency, and usability of their data through a structured self-assessment and group discussion.

The second exercise, *“The Data Journey in GoTriple”*, shifted the discussion to key processes, such as enrichment, data exposition via API, and data visualisation on the discovery platform. Existing providers were to give feedback on how their data is presented and highlighted in GoTriple, while potential new providers could understand GoTriple’s requirements and anticipate integration challenges.

The third exercise, *“Future of the GoTriple community”*, was designed to focus on upcoming developments supported by four European projects, including ATRIUM. Participants would be informed about these initiatives, and data providers’ expectations and feedback would be gathered as the GoTriple team aims to continue delivering added value to its community of data providers.

Although the MLE was designed in English, support was offered to Spanish participants who might have difficulty expressing their thoughts in English.

Agenda

The MLE agenda was the following:

9:00 – Arrival & Welcome coffee

9:30 – Initial speeches

Opening remarks (Pilar Rico, FECYT, OPERAS-ES)

Introduction to the MLE (Carol Delmazo, OPERAS)

Introduction to GoTriple (Julien Homo, FOXCUB; Luca De Santis, NET7)

10:00 – Icebreaker Exercise

10:30 – Interactive Session 1: “Do I know the data I provide?”

Step 1: Self-assessment checklist (30 min)

Step 2: Subgroups exercise (40 min)

11:40 – Coffee Break

12:00 – Step 3: Group synthesis & discussion (40 min-1h)

13:00 – Lunch Break

14:00 – Interactive Session 2: “The Data Journey in GoTriple”

Step 1: Data processing overview (30 min)

Step 2: Subgroups exercise (45 min)

Step 3: Group synthesis & discussion (45 min)

16:00 – Coffee Break

16:30 – Interactive Session 3: “Future of the GoTriple Community”

Step 1: Presentation on GoTriple development (30 min)

Step 2: Group discussion “Strengthening the GoTriple community” (30 min)

17:30 – Wrap-up

3.1 Exercises overview

3.1.1 Exercise 1 - “Do I know the data I provide?”

The first exercise was designed to foster self-awareness among data providers regarding the structure and quality of their own (meta)data. Its main objective was to enable participants to reflect critically on the completeness, consistency, and usability of their datasets, prior to engaging with GoTriple’s integration processes. This activity laid the foundation for mutual understanding by surfacing recurring issues and institutional practices.

To support the process, each participant received a printed instruction sheet outlining the steps of the exercise. This document included clear guidance for individual and group work, a list of discussion topics, and the subgroup composition. It helped ensure a smooth, autonomous execution of the activity even in the absence of constant facilitation.

The session was divided into three steps:

Step 1: Self-assessment checklist (30 min)

Each participant was invited to complete a structured checklist designed to guide a critical review of their institution’s metadata management practices. The GoTriple Data Provider Self-Assessment Checklist covered six core categories:

- Metadata completeness and consistency
- Open access and licensing
- Disciplinary classification and ontologies
- Data quality control
- Technical infrastructure and interoperability
- Multilingual aspects

For each of these categories, participants were asked to assess the current state of their data using a simple scale of *yes/no/partially*. They were also encouraged to reflect on their internal processes – for example, the presence of

validation mechanisms, the use of controlled vocabularies, the availability of APIs or OAI-PMH endpoints, and the treatment of multilingual metadata.

This activity aimed to prompt institutions to move beyond surface-level evaluations and consider the consistency, reliability, and sustainability of their data flows. The checklist was pre-filled with the names of the participating organisations, allowing each institution to directly locate and edit their dedicated tab. Both digital and printed versions were made available, depending on the participants' preferences and equipment. The insights gathered during this phase provided the basis for the collaborative subgroup discussions that followed.

Checklist for Data Provider Self-Assessment (GoTriple)

Organisation name:
Country: /

Metadata Completeness and Consistency

Are authors and affiliations consistently recorded? Yes ▾

Are publication dates or creation dates consistently provided? Yes ▾

Are all original keywords (provided by the data source, if any) present? Yes ▾

Do all resources (e.g. articles) have a DOI? Yes ▾

Are standard metadata schemas used (e.g., Dublin Core, Schema.org)? Yes ▾

Are controlled vocabularies or authority files consistently used? Yes ▾

If yes, are these controlled vocabularies public? Yes ▾

Are date formats standardised across all records? Yes ▾

When applicable, does the metadata include the language attribute? Yes ▾

Open Access and Licensing

Are the licensing terms clearly stated for each resource? Yes ▾

Are resources appropriately marked as open access or restricted? Yes ▾

Are the resources that are marked as open access, really open access (available for download without barriers - e.g. IP address-check, authentication, specific log in...)? Yes ▾

Figure 3 – Screenshot of the Self-Assessment Checklist showing some of the questions.

Step 2: Subgroups exercise (40 min)

This step was designed to promote peer-to-peer exchange by dividing participants into two balanced subgroups composed of both current and prospective data providers. Each group was invited to use whiteboards and sticky notes to visually organise their contributions, following a predefined interactive method. This setup encouraged informal yet structured collaboration, allowing participants to reflect on shared challenges and practices.

Participants were instructed to choose some of the categories they had explored during the self-assessment phase and to add key ideas under each selected theme using stickers. This approach enabled each group to focus on the most relevant issues to their context, while also facilitating pattern recognition and comparison across institutions. A note-taker was present in each group to help steer the discussion when needed, clarify the categories, and ensure that key points were captured and documented accurately.

Due to the disruption caused by the blackout, the groups were restructured on-site, based on the attendees present. The final subgroups were as follows:

- Subgroup A: OAPEN and Biblioteka Nauki (both providers from outside Spain)
- Subgroup B: Complutense University of Madrid (UCM) and RECYT (both based in Spain)

Despite the reduced group size, the activity was carried out as planned. Participants used physical materials to cluster their observations and prepare for the final synthesis phase. Visual documentation of the boards was also collected.

Figure 4 – Participants divided into subgroups working on Exercise 1.

Step 3: Group synthesis & discussion (45 min)

In the final step of Exercise 1, all participants reconvened for a group-wide discussion facilitated by a moderator, with the support of two note-takers. The session began with a brief synthesis: one representative from each subgroup presented the main findings discussed in their group, based on the visual mapping completed in Step 2.

After this synthesis phase, the discussion opened up to the full group. Participants were encouraged to reflect on and react to the insights shared by others, and to address themes that may not have been fully explored during their subgroup work. This structure allowed for a more holistic exchange across institutional experiences and roles.

Two key goals guided this session:

- Enabling participants to gain a clearer understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of their own datasets, through comparison with peers.
- Encouraging the sharing of best practices to support greater alignment and metadata standardisation among data providers.

While structured, the format remained flexible enough to adapt to the contributions of participants. The outcomes of this collective discussion also served as a natural bridge toward the more technical and integrative dimensions addressed in Exercise 2.

Figure 5 - Plenary discussion during Exercise 1, Step 3, with participants sharing subgroup findings and engaging in collective reflection.

3.1.2 Exercise 2 - “The data journey in GoTriple”

This second exercise focused on the technical integration of provider data into the GoTriple platform. Building on the self-assessment work from Exercise 1, it aimed to familiarise participants with key processes such as metadata ingestion, enrichment, visualisation, and API exposure.

Participants were divided into two groups (current and prospective providers), and invited to reflect on their data in light of GoTriple’s integration model. The objective was to surface strengths, gaps, and practical needs through a structured combination of individual analysis and group synthesis.

The exercise unfolded in three phases: a shared walkthrough of the GoTriple pipeline, subgroup analysis using guiding questions, and a final plenary discussion to consolidate findings and identify potential improvements.

Step 1: Data processing overview (30 min)

This step marked the transition from institutional self-assessment to a collective exploration of how metadata is actually processed within the GoTriple platform. It was designed to build a shared technical understanding among all participants, whether current or prospective data providers.

The session opened with a framing presentation (approx. 20 minutes) that walked participants through the end-to-end GoTriple data journey, covering:

- Data harvesting and ingestion from providers,
- Metadata enrichment processes (e.g., normalisation, alignment with multilingual thesauri),
- Search and visualisation features,
- API exposure and interoperability potential.

This overview was essential to ensure that all participants had a clear view of the key concepts and technical processes underlying the GoTriple platform, regardless of their previous involvement.

Figure 6 - Overview session led by the technical team to introduce the key integration and processing steps.

The presentation was followed by a GoTriple Quickfire Quiz (5 minutes), a fast-paced true/false activity designed to reinforce key points in an engaging and informal format. This interactive moment helped anchor the content while encouraging active listening.

The final few minutes were used to introduce the next step of the exercise. Participants were informed that they would now move to a more personalised phase of analysis, applying what they had just learned to their own data context. This progression – from conceptual framing to hands-on reflection – was chosen to gradually lead participants into deeper engagement and prepare the ground for collaborative synthesis in the subgroup work that followed.

Step 1 - GoTriple Quickfire Quiz ⚡

True OR False?

1. GoTriple automatically retrieves all publications from an OAI-PMH repository without any prior configuration.
2. All documents in GoTriple are translated into English via an automatic service.
3. Publication deduplication in GoTriple is based solely on DOI.
4. Annotation with the TRIPLE vocabulary is based on deep learning.
5. The Classify service automatically assigns MORESS disciplines to each document.

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Figure 7 – Example of slide used for the GoTriple Quickfire Quiz during Exercise 2, Step 1

Step 2: Subgroups exercise (45 min)

During this phase, participants engaged in a more in-depth and technical analysis of GoTriple's data integration processes. The activity had two stages: first, participants worked individually with their own datasets; then, they moved into group discussions to share their observations and insights. Clear instructions were available throughout the session, along with a well-defined objective. This not only clarified the goals of the meeting but also helped participants feel more confident – especially in the context of working in a foreign language. The format was intentionally designed to balance individual reflection with collaborative exchange and to accommodate the diverse institutional backgrounds of the participants.

Individual work (20 minutes)

Participants from each institution were invited to reflect on a specific aspect of the GoTriple data pipeline using a tailored set of guiding questions, previously distributed as printed documents. These questions were grouped thematically:

- Group A – Current data providers examined how their datasets are enriched, transformed, and displayed within the GoTriple environment. They were asked to reflect on metadata quality, enrichment accuracy, interoperability with internal taxonomies, and the visibility of their collections (e.g. searchability, attribution).
- Group B – New data providers explored potential alignment with GoTriple’s ingestion and enrichment systems, identifying technical compatibility issues and anticipating challenges related to multilingualism, format transformation, and metadata exposure.

Participants were encouraged to focus on the topic most relevant to their experience and to note observations in the form of short reports or structured bullet points. These reflections were not collected but served as a basis for the next step.

Guiding Questions – Group B: New Providers

Objective: Explore how your dataset aligns with GoTriple's pipeline and requirements.

A. Metadata model & content

- Which fields do you think might require mapping or transformation to match GoTriple's requirements?
- Would your vocabularies be compatible with GoTriple (e.g. multilingual disciplines, content types)?
- Do you foresee issues with multilingual display or translation if integrated into GoTriple?

B. Technical exposure & formats

- Is your current technical setup compatible with GoTriple's ingestion methods (e.g. **OAI-PMH**, file dumps, APIs)?
- Which metadata schemas or formats would need adaptation for GoTriple harvesting (e.g. conversion, mapping)?
- Are your identifiers (e.g. DOI, Handle) and date formats ready to be integrated or require normalisation?

C. Interoperability readiness

- Based on your past experiences with other aggregators (e.g. OpenAIRE, BASE), what worked well and what was challenging?
- Have you identified gaps or mismatches when aligning with shared vocabularies or standards in previous integrations?
- What would you need to facilitate metadata alignment with GoTriple (technical documentation, mapping support, examples)?

D. Potential integration with GoTriple |

Figure 8 - Excerpt from the tailored set of guiding questions for Group B (new data providers).

Joint work (25 minutes)

Participants then regrouped into their respective subgroups (current and prospective providers) to consolidate insights on a visual worksheet using sticky notes. They were invited to complete each section collaboratively, identifying points of convergence or divergence across their institutional contexts.

Each group had a separate task. Current data providers were to analyse how their data is displayed in GoTriple, taking into account strengths and gaps, as well as perceived inconsistencies. Prospective data providers were expected to assess the integration of existing data into GoTriple. Their task was to consider

the key characteristics of the datasets, compatibility with GoTriple and also to identify challenges or expectations.

Group A template	Group B template
(current providers)	(new providers)
<p>In this task, please analyse how your data is displayed in GoTriple. Review your dataset in GoTriple, assess metadata enrichment compared to original data and try to identify strengths, gaps, and inconsistencies of this solution. The outcome should be a structured summary, ideally in the form of a list or a short report that highlights:</p>	<p>In this task, we would like you to explore GoTriple and assess data integration. Please navigate the platform to understand metadata structure, enrichment mechanisms, and search functionalities. Please also identify potential integration challenges for your own data. Based on this, please prepare a structured overview of your dataset and how it could fit into GoTriple.</p>
<p>Strengths: aspects of metadata that are well-structured and effective in GoTriple.</p>	<p>Key characteristics of a dataset: metadata structure, content types, disciplinary scope.</p>
<p>Gaps: missing elements or incomplete metadata that could affect data visibility and usability.</p>	<p>Compatibility with GoTriple: how you're your metadata aligns with GoTriple's format and interoperability standards.</p>
<p>Inconsistencies: discrepancies or formatting issues in the metadata that could impact searchability and interoperability.</p>	<p>Challenges and expectations: potential difficulties in integration and what do you need to facilitate the process.</p>

Figure 9 – Templates on which participants in each group worked

The goals were the following:

- Visualise shared integration challenges and successful practices,
- Highlight variations in technical preparedness,
- Identify actionable needs for alignment, documentation, and support.

In practice, due to the reduced number of participants, the two groups were redefined on-site. The final subgroups were as follows:

- Subgroup A (Current providers): Biblioteka Nauki and RECYT,
- Subgroup B (New providers): OAPEN and UCM.

This distribution deviated slightly from the original plan, as some institutions were reassigned to a different category to maintain meaningful dialogue and ensure complementarity between participants. The collaborative boards served as the groundwork for the final plenary discussion in Step 3.

Figure 10 – Subgroup A synthesising findings during the subgroup analysis phase of Exercise 2

Step 3: Group synthesis & discussion (45 min)

In the final phase of Exercise 2, all participants reconvened to share the outcomes of their subgroup discussions. Each group was invited to briefly present the key insights from their reflections, drawing on the whiteboard notes and clustered sticky cards from the previous step.

Although no formal presentation was required, subgroups were encouraged to highlight a few central points of agreement, disagreement, or specific challenges encountered. The aim was not only to identify technical issues, but also to uncover recurring patterns, common needs, and potential areas for improving metadata integration workflows. The session concluded with a collective summary, resulting in a set of actionable recommendations based on the insights gathered.

This session also allowed for open exchanges between current and prospective providers, facilitating cross-learning and revealing how different experiences (e.g., data ingestion, multilingual issues, enrichment, interoperability) played out in real contexts.

The collective discussion was moderated to ensure each participant could contribute and to keep the session within time. The insights gathered will inform future adjustments to the GoTriple ingestion pipeline and documentation.

Figure 11 – Collective debrief during Step 3: discussion of shared challenges, opportunities, and recommendations

3.1.3 Exercise 3 - “Future of the GoTriple community”

The final session of the Mutual Learning Exercise was structured in two steps, each focusing on a different but complementary aspect of GoTriple’s future. The first step invited participants to assess and prioritise possible directions for future technical development, while the second opened a broader discussion on

how to strengthen the GoTriple community through shared practices and emerging initiatives.

Together, these two components aimed to gather targeted feedback on envisaged developments of the platform and to explore potential synergies with other aggregators, projects, and communities.

Step 1: Presentation on GoTriple development (30 min)

This session opened with a short presentation introducing three strategic directions for the future of GoTriple, with the aim of understanding which features would bring the most value to data providers:

- Data Provider Dashboards
 - Access to basic statistics on your data
 - Usage data and visibility metrics
 - Citation tracking
 - Metadata quality assessments

- GoTriple Data Science Tools
 - APIs for data access and analysis
 - Integration with external analytical tools
 - Support for bibliometric use cases

- GoTriple White Label Software
 - Ability to set up your own discovery service (for a specific discipline, country, or domain)
 - Participation in a federated infrastructure for metadata

Participants were invited to vote on each direction on a shared whiteboard by assigning a score of 1 (low relevance), 2 (moderate relevance), or 3 (high relevance) according to their vision. Each strategic direction was represented by a column and participants added their rating under each one.

Participants were asked:

- What motivated your scores?

- What would make these features more useful to your institution?
- Are there any complementary needs not yet addressed?

This step aimed to support a user-informed development roadmap, grounded in providers' actual needs and expectations for value-added services.

Figure 12 - Prioritisation of future GoTriple developments using the 1-2-3 rating method.

Step 2: Group discussion "Strengthening the GoTriple community" (30 min)

The final part of Exercise 3 shifted focus from feature prioritisation to community building and knowledge sharing. Participants were invited to reflect on their broader ecosystem and respond to a set of open prompts aimed at strengthening the GoTriple community:

- How can the GoTriple community be strengthened in the long run?

- What kinds of support, collaboration formats, or shared resources would be valuable?
- Are you already aggregated by other services?
- What has worked well or poorly in these experiences? What lessons can be drawn?
- Are there any new initiatives, major projects, or developments you'd like to share?

The discussion was conducted in plenary and encouraged informal contributions. Several participants shared reflections on past integration projects, success factors in data aggregation, and current developments in their respective institutions. This step concluded the session with a broader perspective, anchoring the day's technical focus within a long-term, collaborative vision for the GoTriple ecosystem.

3.2 Event logistics and mitigation of the historic blackout

The event took place on April 29, 2025, at the FECYT office in the National Museum of Science and Technology (MUNCYT) in Madrid, Spain. Communication with participants began two months prior to the event to ensure they were informed and prepared. This communication was primarily conducted via email, in English, Spanish or Polish, depending on the case.

To provide participants with clear and comprehensive information, an informational brochure was prepared. Developed in English, it included the following details:

- An overview of the MLE
- A description of the ATRIUM project
- Information about the GoTriple platform
- Instructions for registering on the GoTriple platform
- Event details, including a link to the agenda
- Directions to the event venue, including a link to a PDF with guidance for travel arrangements and accommodation suggestions
- Contact details

Participants also received an *Information on Data Processing and Declaration of Consent* document, with a request to review and accept its content.

Catering services were provided. Additionally, reimbursement documentation was collected, as accommodation was covered by the ATRIUM project. Following the MLE, participants were asked to complete a feedback form.

Historic blackout

As already mentioned, the day before the first ATRIUM MLE, Spain and Portugal suffered a historic blackout that left both countries without electricity for hours. The organising team had already arrived in Madrid and managed to do a rehearsal of the event despite the power outage. However, this situation affected the MLE in two ways: first, participants from four invited institutions were unable to attend, and second, the exercises needed to be adjusted. Despite this unfortunate incident, the event logistics ran smoothly for those who managed to attend. Those who could not attend will be contacted in a second stage to support their onboarding to GoTriple and may be invited to future events.

Figure 13 - Participants of the first ATRIUM Mutual Learning Exercise, Madrid, 29 April 2025.

4. Key takeaways

In the first exercise, *“Do I Know the Data I Provide?”*, participants reflected critically on the heterogeneity of metadata supplied by different providers. While larger services often employ standardised schemas and automated validation procedures, smaller platforms frequently rely on manual curation or the submission of raw spreadsheets, leading to inconsistent or incomplete metadata records. This discrepancy underscores **the need for GoTriple as an aggregator to take the responsibility for preliminary metadata validation and normalisation**. By doing so, GoTriple can ensure quality across its data and take off the technical burden of individual providers. A parallel consensus emerged regarding licensing: **the adoption of Creative Commons Zero (CC0) for metadata dissemination was widely seen as optimal**, facilitating unrestricted reuse and further enrichment by both the GoTriple platform and the broader scholarly community. Moreover, discussions of discipline classification have revealed an abundance of schemes – from THEMA¹⁵ to various national taxonomies. Participants noted that the **lack of a common scheme calls for further mapping efforts**. In this context, **GoTriple is positioned to lead by offering harmonisation tools that align divergent classification systems to a common framework**. Finally, participants highlighted the persistent challenge of multilingual metadata: although English-language abstracts are routinely required, titles and keywords frequently lack translation. This gap presents **an opportunity for GoTriple to integrate automatic translation modules, thereby enhancing the global discoverability of scholarly outputs within SSH**.

The second exercise, *“The Data Journey in GoTriple”*, guided participants through the technical pipeline of data ingestion and enrichment within GoTriple. Contributors confirmed that most of them can expose their collections via OAI-PMH endpoints – employing Dublin Core, EDM, XOAI, or DC-BASE – or by providing MARC21 and OpenAIRE dumps. Initial tests of data collection from new providers proved largely problem-free, indicating that **aggregation by GoTriple does not necessarily impose additional burdens on the institution providing the data**. At the same time, it was noted that certain metadata elements, such

¹⁵ <https://www.editeur.org/151/thema>

as bibliographic references and funding information, are available from the GoTriple API perspective but are not consistently indexed or displayed in the user interface. This omission can create a perception of data inaccessibility and limit the efficiency of advanced filtering options. Accordingly, **providers advocated for the ability to download search results and to receive detailed enrichment metrics**, such as counts of translated abstracts or assigned disciplinary labels, to monitor the performance of GoTriple's processing pipeline. Despite these concerns, participants acknowledged that the **core functionalities (deduplication, automated classification, and semantic annotation) operate effectively behind the scenes**, enabling the aggregation of diverse SSH resources into coherent thematic clusters.

In the third exercise, "*Future of the GoTriple Community*", the discussion turned to the strategic evolution of the GoTriple ecosystem. Participants emphasised that **enhancements to the analytics dashboard should focus not on aesthetic redesign but on the expansion of substantive metrics**, such as the citation counts, usage statistics, and language distributions, as well as on the **integration with institutional reporting systems**. The prospect of implementing the **white labeling** within the LUMEN project has attracted a lot of interest, as it would **enable disciplinary networks or national consortia to customise their own GoTriple instances**. However, successful adoption will depend on **comprehensive training workshops conducted in national languages** and the provision of specialised support materials. Across all discussions, there was unanimous agreement that **sustained, two-way communication, ranging from pre-harvest validation reports to one-on-one technical consultations and national node meetings, is the cornerstone of trust-building**. In this way, transparency and relational engagement are not mere add-ons, but the driving force behind the continued growth and vitality of the GoTriple community.

5. Reflections on the MLE format

The first ATRIUM MLE was initially planned for a larger group of participants from eight institutions, including current and prospective data providers, to ensure qualitative work and broader representation. However, due to the blackout, we were able to work with only four institutions. On the one hand, the smaller group size had a positive effect, enabling more intensive and qualitative work. On the other hand, the higher engagement level required from the participants led to noticeable fatigue. Hence, we recommend organizing a mutual learning exercise with representatives of 6-8 institutions. It allows for qualitative work while ensuring increased scope of data providers representation.

The first ATRIUM MLE aimed to engage Spanish data providers for GoTriple, but also included institutions from Poland and the Netherlands. The event primarily used English as its working language, with Spanish support available when necessary. This may have discouraged local attendees from expressing their thoughts more often. Therefore, we recommend carefully considering the target audience when designing the event: whether the focus should be on the local context and language, or on reaching an international audience. If the event targets the local community, the organisers could consider conducting the event in the local language in order to ensure a more natural flow of discussion.

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